

REVIEWS

Article Review “Phenomenological Perspective in Researching Immigrant Children’s Experience”, authors Batuchina A., Straksiene G.

Alaverdov E. V. (Reviewer)¹

¹ *Georgian Technical University, Georgia*

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Information about the author: *Alaverdov Emilia Vidiatovna – <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3282-172X>; emily-78@mail.ru; Doctor of Social Science, Associate Professor, Georgian Technical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.*

Review:

The article of Batuchina and Straksiene “Phenomenological Perspective in Researching Immigrant Children’s Experience” has been published in the International Journal of Science Annals, Vol. 2, No. 1-2, 2019.

Migration became one of the most acute problems of the modern world, which involves both political and social spectrums and became a very complex problem, which is very difficult to study from the Phenomenological Perspective. Everyone is well aware that to manage such large surges of migrants is practically impossible, as, for the scientists, they even do not have a united approach to the research of this unsolved phenomenon.

For certain reasons people, in most cases, families have to change their dwelling spaces, to move from one country or city to another. Without even considering the physiological stress of the family members, especially children or elderlies. Among the many problems, which migrants face in a host country the most acute one is an adaptation. There is a mistaken perception that children adapt to every novelty and situation easily than adults, however, in this regards children are the most vulnerable. Here the problem is that in most cases, children are not even listed, since parents are concerned about searching for jobs and finding the ways to adapt to a new space.

The authors explain that the meaning of migration is minimized for children and that adults do not pay attention to it. However, the experience of grown-ups draws significant attention.

The authors pay attention to the moment that children leave all their belongings and move to a new unknown country where they face difficulties.

Despite that, the paper is well developed and the conclusion reflects the results of the study; however, it speaks only about the problem and does not give any recommendations, how to solve it. It would be good if the author gives suggestions and recommendations about what can be done to mitigate the situation to reduce the children's stress. I think after the conclusion there should be a small part of suggestions and recommendations. Moreover, it would be better if the author uses the Comparative research method, which is exactly used for cross-cultural studies, as the issue of migration straightly deals with cross-cultural studies. Besides, I would like to highlight that while studying the problem of child migration the authors did not consider the cultural or religious factors. As I understood from the discussions, they conducted their research among the migrants within Europe, or labor migrants from the Post-soviet countries since they do not even mention the problems of cultural adaptation. It would be good if they continue their study among the children migrants from the Middle East. After the Arab Spring, Europe continues to receive a large number of Muslim migrants, with very different culture and worldview. Europe indeed does its best to reduce the numbers of newcomers through the strict border control and tightening the refugees and asylum seekers Packages. However, the problem is still acute, in this regard, the most important is that, besides the difficulties of traveling and adaptation, at the same time the Muslim migrants face harassment from the host society, and here the children since they are undefended again appear in a very vulnerable situation. They not only have trouble in a new environment but they feel unwelcomed and unsecured in the context of cultural and religious differences.

Thus, it is worth saying that the experience of migrant children requires a thorough study. In this case, the main objective of Researching Immigrant Children's Experience should be, firstly the awareness of their psychological situation and conditions, and the development of effective ways to their adaptation and integration to the new environment, considering their cultural aspects.

Reference

Batuchina, A., & Straksiene, G. (2019). Phenomenological Perspective in Researching Immigrant Children's Experience. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 2(1-2), 26–32. doi:10.26697/ijsa.2019.1-2.04

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